

Bridging the Gap Between Natural Language and Semantic Web: A Text-to-SPARQL System

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Abstract. At the core of our research is a text-to-SPARQL query generation system that bridges natural language understanding with semantic data retrieval. The system leverages LLM agents with planning and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) capabilities alongside Wikidata API search to improve entity linking and efficiently retrieve candidate entities from Wikidata, while multiple Wikidata embedding strategies are explored to enhance retrieval accuracy.

By automatically transforming user questions into precise SPARQL queries, our methodology ensures scalable extraction of information from large knowledge graphs. Multi-query ranking algorithms further refine the process, enhancing both the relevance and accuracy of retrieved results.

Evaluation using the QALD dataset over multilingual Wikidata entities demonstrates the robustness and versatility of our solution, paving the way for more intelligent, user-friendly, and adaptable tools for navigating complex knowledge systems.

Keywords: Knowledge graph question answering, LLM agent, Wikidata, embedding, Semantic Web

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) have revolutionized the field of Question Answering (QA) over Knowledge Graphs (KGQA) [1] by enabling more natural interactions with structured data. However, despite their impressive language understanding capabilities, LLMs often struggle to generate precise queries required for effective knowledge retrieval. This limitation is particularly identified when bridging questions in natural language with the formal semantics of SPARQL queries used to query knowledge graphs like Wikidata. Additionally, many users lack the technical expertise needed to manually write SPARQL queries, while LLMs are limited by their training data, which may not fully capture the latest updates in complex knowledge graphs.

To overcome these challenges, this study introduces a novel text-to-SPARQL query generation system that integrates LLM agents [2] with planning and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) capabilities [3]. This integration not only resolves entity disambiguation but also accelerates the retrieval of candidate

entities from Wikidata. In addition, multiple Wikidata embedding approaches are explored to optimize retrieval efficiency and accuracy, ultimately enabling scalable and domain-agnostic KGQA. The multi-query ranking algorithm is used to select the most relevant query among several candidates, thereby boosting both precision and overall system performance.

This integrated approach sets a new benchmark in the realm of KGQA by addressing the inherent limitations of traditional fine-tuning and rigid query architectures. By transforming natural language questions into semantically rich SPARQL queries, the proposed system advances the interaction between natural language processing and semantic web technologies. Evaluation of the QALD dataset with multilingual Wikidata entities emphasizes the robustness and versatility of this solution, paving the way for more intelligent, user-friendly, and adaptable tools for navigating complex knowledge systems.

2 Related Work

Early KGQA research focused on translating natural language questions into formal queries like SPARQL by leveraging linguistic structures. PANTO’s approach [4] decomposes queries into nominal-phrase pairs using deep parsing and maps them to ontology triples (subject, predicate, object), capturing semantic relations via verb phrases and prepositions.

Benchmarking datasets have been crucial in advancing KGQA. The QALD-10 dataset [5] addresses challenges such as poor multilingual translation, simple gold-standard queries, and weak experiment replicability by offering 412 training and 394 test multilingual question-query pairs executable on a stable Wikidata endpoint. Other notable benchmarks include CRAG [6] and Context Graph [7].

Transformer-based methods have improved context integration in KGQA. MST5 [8] enhances SPARQL generation by appending extracted entities and linguistic context to the query before feeding it to a language model. However, it struggles with low-resource languages and limited training data. THINK-ON-GRAPH 2.0 [9] and the method in [10] offer variations that focus on entity linking and triplet correction.

Recently, Dynamic Few-Shot Learning (DFSL) [11], very similar to SymKGQA [12], has emerged as an effective paradigm for KGQA. DFSL retrieves similar question-SPARQL pairs to guide the model through in-context learning, mitigating triple-flip errors by generating multiple query candidates.

Despite progress, no method achieves consistently reliable, multilingual, and domain-agnostic query generation. This highlights the need for continued research into robust, generalizable KGQA systems.

3 Methodology

Our approach attempts to bridge the gap between natural languages and the semantic web. Integrates LLM agents with RAG capabilities and the dynamic few-

shot learning (DFSL) method with two distinct ways for entity retrieval: an earlier Wikidata API service, which is based on Elastic Search, and an embedding-based method utilizing a Wikidata turtle dump [13]. Both approaches follow a similar pipeline for Name Entity Recognition (NER), in-context prompt construction, and multi-query generation, but differ in how candidate entities are retrieved.

Fig. 1. Our pipeline for bridging natural language and the semantic web. The system uses entity retrieval methods via Wikidata API search with components for NER extraction, in-context prompt construction, and multi-query generation.

Before entering the system’s pipeline¹, our system first attempts a zero-shot [14] query generation for straightforward questions. In this step, the LLM is prompted directly with the prompt shown in Fig. 1 to generate a SPARQL query without relying on additional context or external entity linking. This attempt serves as a fast solution for simple queries that may not require the full pipeline. If the zero-shot approach succeeds in answering the question upon query execution, the process terminates early, thereby reducing computational time. However, when the zero-shot approach fails to return results, the system enters the pipeline with more advanced processing steps.

¹ The code and pipeline outputs are available on this GitHub repository.

The next step of our pipeline is processing the question using Named Entity Recognition (NER) to extract candidate Wikidata entity labels. In this step, the prompt shown in Fig. 1 is used to identify proper names, such as organizations, persons, and locations, as well as key common nouns and verbs that are important to understanding the question’s context. These candidate labels, along with the input question, are passed to the next steps of the system.

Our first approach to entity retrieval was using the Wikidata API with an Elastic Search service [15] to find related entities with the extracted candidate entities. While this method achieved moderate precision in entity-linking, several limitations were identified. First, the questions are often ambiguous, making it hard to match the extracted candidate labels with the actual entity names in Wikidata, reducing the precision of the retrieval. Additionally, Wikidata API search may struggle with the multilingual nature of Wikidata, as its indexing and matching mechanisms might not effectively capture language-specific words.

A critical component of our pipeline is the use of Dynamic Few-Shot Learning (DFSL) examples, which serve as contextual demonstrations for the language model during query generation. Instead of relying on static, hand-picked examples, our approach dynamically retrieves relevant examples based on the semantic similarity between the user’s input and embedded KGQA pairs. Each DFSL example consists of a question and the corresponding SPARQL query. These examples are taken and embedded from datasets such as LCQuad 2.0 [16], ensuring that they represent a wide range of query structures and complexities. When a new question is received, the system encodes it in a vector representation using a sentence encoder. This vector is then compared against the vectors of all stored DFSL examples. The most similar examples are dynamically selected and concatenated with the input question to form an in-context prompt.

This retrieval process allows the LLM to use prior examples that are most relevant to the current query, thus enhancing its ability to generate accurate and semantically coherent SPARQL queries.

Now that we have all the information needed to create the SPARQL query, the next step is to formulate a well-structured prompt for the LLM, as shown in Fig. 1. In our approach, we use Llama-3.1:70B [17] model. We construct the prompt using three components: the user’s question Q , dynamically retrieved examples Ex , and semantically similar entity information S . This prompt instructs Llama-3 to generate a SPARQL query I , specifying whether a "SELECT" or "ASK" query is appropriate, while enforcing a strict JSON output format containing only the query. We provide detailed contextual information and clear output guidelines in the prompt. This approach helps mitigate common errors, such as subject-object inversions, thereby enhancing the overall accuracy and precision of the generated SPARQL queries.

The query generation process is designed to be robust against initial failures. If this initial query fails to return a valid answer, the system initiates a loop that generates up to five alternative queries, using the same extracted entities and relations. If none of these five queries provide a valid result, the system does not terminate the process. Instead, as illustrated in Fig. 1, it returns to

earlier stages in the pipeline, such as re-extracting entities and relations from the input question or selecting different QA examples. The entire fallback process can repeat for up to three full cycles, ensuring multiple opportunities to recover from issues such as incorrect entity linking or relation detection.

The multi-query strategy is iterative. It significantly increases the likelihood of generating a valid and precise SPARQL query, even for ambiguous or complex questions. Additionally, it helps mitigate common LLM-related errors, such as the triple-flip problem, where the subject and object roles are incorrectly assigned within the query.

4 Results

To see the initial impact of the system, the evaluation was performed using the GERBIL QA benchmarking platform [18], which has been widely used for KGQA systems. GERBIL allows for standardized evaluations through its web interface, ensuring reproducibility and comparability between different systems. The evaluation results were uploaded, providing scores, system descriptions, and standardized metrics for benchmarking. Our system achieved a **Macro F1 score of 0.45533** on the QALD-10 dataset using the Wikidata API search for entity retrieval², highlighting the effectiveness of our overall pipeline. To better understand the contribution of different components, we also evaluated variations of our approach. An approach without the zero-shot component resulted in a Macro F1 score of 0.1664, indicating the significance of this module for handling previously unseen questions³. Furthermore, a version of the system without the few-shot learning capabilities scored 0.141, demonstrating the importance of providing in-context examples for improving performance⁴. This result demonstrates that the pipeline has room for improvement.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we presented a novel text-to-SPARQL query generation system that uses dynamic few-shot learning in conjunction with advanced entity retrieval strategies for Knowledge Graph Question Answering. Our approach addresses the challenges associated with translating questions from natural language into precise SPARQL queries, especially when users lack the technical skills to formulate these queries manually.

We initially implemented a Wikidata API search entity retrieval method, which, when integrated with DFSL examples and a multi-query generation strategy, showed good results. This result demonstrates the viability of our pipeline while also highlighting limitations in semantic precision and handling entity mismatches.

² <https://gerbil-qa.aksw.org/gerbil/experiment?id=202501240025>

³ <https://gerbil-qa.aksw.org/gerbil/experiment?id=202506060001>

⁴ <https://gerbil-qa.aksw.org/gerbil/experiment?id=202506060002>

To overcome this, we explored an embedding retrieval mechanism. By benchmarking several embedding models, we selected `intfloat/multilingual-e5-small` for its excellent multilingual capabilities and fast speed. This embedding approach promises to enhance entity linking precision by capturing deeper semantic relationships and handling diverse query formulations more effectively.

Future work will focus on scaling the embedding approach to process the entire Wikidata dump, implementing answer selection strategies, and extending multilingual support across various domains. This effort is expected to further bridge the gap between natural language understanding and semantic data retrieval, making the way for more intelligent, user-friendly, and domain-agnostic KGQA systems.

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